

Title: The Metaphysics behind the Jiva Upakar Tantra of ancient Kamarupa and its application to bio-social healing

Author(s): Rupam Das^{1,2}, Sonali Das^{1,2,3}, Tutumoni Baishya^{1,2}, Sainen Ch. Baishya^{1,2}, Prajña Paramita Dutta^{1,2}, Bikul Das^{1,2,3*}

¹Centre for Vedic Altruism, KaviKrishna Laboratory, IIT-Guwahati Research Park, Guwahati, Assam, India.

²Department of Medical Humanities, KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care, Sualkuchi, Assam, India.

³Thoreau Laboratory for Global Health, University of Massachusetts, Lowell, Massachusetts.

rupamslkdas@gmail.com,
sonalidas14@gmail.com,
tutu.monibaishya@gmail.com,
sbsualkuchi@gmail.com,
dutta.prajna@gmail.com,

*Corresponding author, Email:
bdas@kavikrishnalab.org

Jiva Upakara Tantra (JUT) is a unique tantra philosophy of Ancient Kamrupa that emerged in the 6th-7th century. The metaphysics of this Tantra philosophy is based on the theory of Avatar Vad of Vaishnavism. According to the AvatarBaad theory, when righteousness decreases in a society, Lord Vishnu manifests himself on earth as an avatar. In his avatar forms, he has the ability to kill the demons and establish Dharma, restoring the balance of the society. Similarly, according to Jiva Upakara Tantra, when our body undergoes stress, such as illness, an Avatar Kosha is activated. The Avatar Kosha's activation in turn causes the activation of our body's energy fluids known as "Sahasa-Ojash". The enhanced flow of the Sahasa-Ojash boosts the immunity of our body as it fights against the disease. In summary, the key metaphysics of JUT is centered around the activation of the Avatar Kosha and the flow of the Sahasa-Ojash in the mind-body. Beyond the body's fitness, this AvatarBaad theory of JUT also applies to social and material factors also like how any

social situation reacts during stress and how Avatar Kosha is activated to sustain and rise. On the basis of this philosophy, a satra and temple-based bio-social healing or Cikitsha Satra is developed in the Sualkuchi-Hajo area of ancient Kamrupa. KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care is operating in this area for the last two-and-half-decades to reorganize this ancient healing practice in rural health by developing the Vedic Altruism based telemedicine care at KaviKrishna Telemedicine Care. This satra/temple network is now used for our social network analysis to study Avatar Kosha in a temple network community. Covid-19 Home care study activated by KTC during the covid-19 pandemic suggesting the emergence of Avatar Kosha in Sualkuchi-Hajo cultural complex.